

A New Synthetic Approach to Amidino thiolurethanes and Amidino carbamides

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Interaction of carbonyl sulphide with *p*-chlorophenyl and *p*-tolyl guanidines in presence of alkyl halides has been shown to afford the related alkyl guanyl thiocarbamates. These on reaction with amines eliminate mercaptan and form the corresponding amidino carbamides.

INTERACTION of amines with carbonyl sulphide, like carbon disulphide, is known^{1a} to result in the formation of the related amine salts of the corresponding thiocarbamic acid (II) and can be stated as follows (Chart 1):

where, R = alkyl-

Chart 1

p-Chlorophenyl- and *p*-tolyl guanidines unlike other primary amines do not react with carbonyl sulphide in acetone medium but if the reaction is carried out in presence of an alkyl halide, the related thiol esters of the corresponding amidine thiocarbamic acids are obtained. The reaction, evidently, can be stated as shown in the Chart 2.

Where, R, R' and R'' are as above.

Chart 4

Where in, (a) R = *p*-chlorophenyl- and R' = methyl-
(b) R = *p*-chlorophenyl- and R' = ethyl-
(c) R = *p*-chlorophenyl- and R' = allyl-
(d) R = *p*-tolyl- and R' = methyl-
(e) R = *p*-tolyl- and R' = ethyl-
(f) R = *p*-tolyl- and R' = allyl-

Chart 2

As expected, the thiol esters or amidino thiouretanes (IV) on reaction with amines eliminated mercaptan and formed the related amidinocarbamides (V). Thus:

Where in, (a) R = *p*-chlorophenyl- and R'' = phenyl-
(b) R = R'' = *p*-chlorophenyl-
(c) R = *p*-chlorophenyl- and R'' = isopropyl-
(d) R = *p*-tolyl- and R'' = phenyl-
(e) R = R'' = *p*-tolyl-

Chart 3

The identity of the amidino carbamides (Va, b, d & e) has been confirmed by comparison with authentic samples obtained by the interaction of appropriate guanidine and thioester^{2,3} of thiocarbamic acids (VI) as shown in Chart 4

Experimental

1. Interaction of carbonyl sulphide with *p*-chlorophenyl and *p*-tolyl guanidines :

Carbonyl sulphide was prepared by the interaction of ammonium thiocyanate and sulphuric acid as per procedure described earlier^{1b}. It was purified and dried by passing it through an aqueous 33% sodium hydroxide solution followed by concentrated sulphuric acid. The gas was then passed through dry* acetone (50 ml) until the latter was saturated with it. To this saturated solution of carbonyl sulphide in acetone the alkyl halide (*vide infra*) and *p*-chlorophenyl-⁴/*p*-tolyl guanidine⁴ were added and a slow stream of carbonyl sulphide passed for a further period of about 2 hr. Presence of traces of hydrogen sulphide and the related mercaptan was noticed in the effluent gas. The reaction mixture was worked out as follows :

On evaporation of the acetone at room temperature, a colourless sticky residue was left behind which on basification with aqueous ammonia afforded a solid; this was filtered out and crystallised from ethanol or aqueous ethanol. It was identified as the related thiol ester of *p*-chlorophenyl-/*p*-tolyl guanidine thiocarbamic acid (IV; *vide* experiments 1a to f) through analysis and reaction with amines, when the corresponding 1,3-disubstituted amidino carbamides (V) were obtained (*vide* experiments 2a-e).

The aqueous ammoniacal filtrate on acidification with hydrochloric acid and addition of sodium bicarbonate precipitated the unreacted guanidine as its carbonate.

(a) *Methyl p-chlorophenyl guanidine thiocarbamate (IVa)* : *p*-Chlorophenyl guanidine (5.0 g), carbonyl sulphide and methyl iodide (5.0 ml) on reaction as above yielded IVa (3.0 g); m.p. 141° (d); (Found : N, 17.3%; C₉H₁₀N₃OCl requires N, 17.2%). On stirring in a little hydrobromic acid it formed a hydrobromide, m.p. 115° (d); (Found : N, 12.9%; mol. equiv. determined acidimetrically in an ethanolic medium, 324; C₉H₁₀N₃OCl, HBr requires N, 12.9%; mol. equiv. 324.5).

(b) *Ethyl p-chlorophenyl guanidine thiocarbamate (IVb)* : *p*-Chlorophenyl guanidine (5.0 g), carbonyl sulphide and ethyl bromide (5.0 ml) on reaction as above yielded IVb (1.8 g); m.p. 130° (d); (Found : N, 16.0%; C₁₀H₁₂N₃OCl requires N, 16.3%). It formed a hydrobromide, m.p. 115° (d); (Found : N, 12.5%; mol. equiv. determined acidimetrically, 327; C₁₀H₁₂N₃OCl, HBr requires N, 12.4%; mol. equiv. 338.5).

(c) *Allyl p-chlorophenyl guanidine thiocarbamate (IVc)* : *p*-Chlorophenyl guanidine (5.0 g), carbonyl sulphide and allyl bromide (5.0 ml) on reaction as above yielded IVc (2.7 g); m.p. 128° (d); (Found : N, 15.8; C₁₁H₁₂N₃OCl requires N, 15.6%). It formed a hydrobromide, m.p. 161° (d); (Found :

N, 11.9%, mol. equiv. determined acidimetrically 350; C₁₁H₁₂N₃OCl, HBr requires N, 11.9%; mol. equiv. 350.5).

(d) *Methyl p-tolyl guanidine thiocarbamate (IVd)* : *p*-Tolyl guanidine (5.0 g), methyl iodide and carbonyl sulphide (5.0 ml) on reaction as above yielded IVd (3.0 g); m.p. 120° (d); (Found : C, 54.1; H, 6.1; N, 18.8%; C₁₀H₁₃N₃OS requires C, 53.8; H, 5.8; N, 18.8%). It formed a hydrobromide, m.p. 165° (d); (Found : N, 14.0%; mol. equiv. determined acidimetrically, 297; C₁₀H₁₃N₃OS, HBr requires N, 13.8%; mol. equiv. 305).

(e) *Ethyl p-tolyl guanidine thiocarbamate (IVe)* : *p*-Tolyl guanidine (5.0 g), ethyl bromide and carbonyl sulphide (5.0 ml) on reaction as above afforded IVe (1.5 g), m.p. 116° (d); (Found : C, 55.9; H, 6.2; N, 16.8%; C₁₂H₁₅N₃OS requires C, 57.8; H, 6.0; N, 16.8%). It formed a hydrobromide, m.p. 152° (d); (Found : N, 12.4; Br, 24.1%, mol. equiv. determined acidimetrically, 327; C₁₂H₁₅N₃OS, HBr requires N, 12.7; Br, 24.2%; mol. equiv. 330).

2. Interaction of amines with alkyl guanidine thiocarbamates (IV) : Formation of the related amidino carbamides (V) :

When a 1 : 1 mixture of the above ester and the amine were heated under reflux in benzene medium until the evolution of the related mercaptan ceased, a colourless microcrystalline product separated out, which was filtered. In all the cases it was found crystallisable from ethanol or aqueous ethanol and was identified as the expected amidino carbamide.

(a) *1-Phenyl-3-p-chlorophenylamidino carbamide (Va)* : Methyl *p*-chlorophenyl guanidine thiocarbamate (IVa, 1.0 g) on reaction with aniline (1.0 ml) afforded Va (0.8 g); m.p. 188° (d); (Found : N, 18.7%; C₁₄H₁₃N₄OCl requires N, 19.4%). It formed a hydrobromide, m.p. 178° (d); (Found : N, 15.0%, mol. equiv. determined acidimetrically, 373; C₁₄H₁₃N₄OCl, HBr requires N, 15.0%, mol. equiv. 369.5). These have been identified as 1-phenyl-3-*p*-chlorophenyl amidino carbamide (Va) and its hydrobromide respectively. The i.r. spectrum of the former was found superimposable with that of an authentic sample prepared as described in the experiment 3a. Also, no depression was observed in its m.p. (178° (d)) on mixing with an authentic sample.

Other esters (IVb and c) also on reaction with aniline formed the same amidino carbamide (Va).

(b) *1-p-Chlorophenyl-3-p-chlorophenyl amidino carbamide (Vb)* : Methyl *p*-chlorophenyl thiocarbamate (IVa; 1.3 g) on reaction as above with *p*-chloroaniline (0.8 g), afforded Vb (1.0 g). It was found to sinter at 192° and melt at 335°; (Found : N, 17.4%; C₁₄H₁₂N₄OCl₂ requires N, 17.3%). It has been identified as 1-*p*-chlorophenyl-3-*p*-chlorophenylamidino carbamide (Vb) through its undepressed m.m.p. (sinters at 192° and melts at 335°) and superimposable i.r. spectrum with that of an authentic sample prepared as described in experiment 3b.

Other esters (IVb and c) also on reaction with *p*-chloroaniline formed the same amidino carbamide (Vb).

* The reactants and solvent should be well dried, otherwise carbonate of the reacting guanidine is formed due to the hydrolysis of carbonyl sulphide^{1c} into carbon dioxide and hydrogen sulphide and the former reacting with the starting guanidine.

(c) 1-Isopropyl-3-*p*-chlorophenylamidino carbamide (Vc): A mixture of benzene solution of isopropyl amine dried over ignited sodium sulphate and ethyl *p*-chlorophenyl guanidine thiocarbamate (IVb, 0.4 g) was heated under reflux until evolution of ethyl mercaptan ceased. On evaporation at room temperature a colourless residue (0.4 g) was left behind; it was crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 172°(d); (Found: N, 21.8%; Calcd. for $C_{11}H_{15}N_4OCl$; N, 22.0%). It formed a hydrobromide, m.p. 125°(d); mol. equiv. determined acidimetrically, 335; $C_{11}H_{15}N_4OCl$, HBr requires mol. equiv. 335.5. These have been identified as 1-isopropyl-3-*p*-chlorophenylamidino carbamide (Vc; Lit.⁵ m.p. 172°-4°) and its hydrobromide respectively.

Other esters (IVa and c) also on reaction with isopropylamine formed the same amidino carbamide (Vc).

(d) 1-Phenyl-3-*p*-tolylamidino carbamide (Vd): Methyl *p*-tolyl guanidine thiocarbamate (IVd; 2.0 g) on reaction with aniline (1.0 ml) afforded Vd (1.5 g); it was found to sinter at 175° and melt at 335°; (Found: C, 67.1; H, 5.9; N, 20.5%; $C_{15}H_{16}N_4O$ requires C, 67.1; H, 6.0; N, 20.8%). It has been identified as 1-phenyl-3-*p*-tolylamidino carbamide (Vd) through its undepressed m.m.p. (sinters at 175° and melts at 335°) and superimposable i.r. spectrum with that of an authentic sample prepared as described in experiment 3c.

Other esters (IVe and f) also on reaction with aniline formed the same amidino carbamide (Vd).

(e) 1-*p*-Tolyl-3-*p*-tolylamidino carbamide (Ve): Methyl *p*-tolyl guanidine thiocarbamate (IVd; 0.5 g) on reaction with *p*-toluidine (0.3 g) afforded Ve (0.5 g); it sinters at 215° and melts at 335° (d); (Found: C, 66.3; H, 6.5; N, 19.7%; $C_{16}H_{18}N_4O$ requires C, 68.1; H, 6.4; N, 19.9%). This has been identified as 1-*p*-tolyl-3-*p*-tolylamidino carbamide (Ve) through its undepressed m.m.p. (sinters at 215° and melts at 335° (d) and superimposable i.r. spectrum with that of an authentic sample prepared as described in the experiment 3d.

Other esters (IVe and f) also on reaction with *p*-toluidine formed the same amidino carbamide (Ve).

3. Preparation of authentic samples of the 1-substituted-3-substituted amidino carbamides:

On the interaction of appropriate guanidine and the ethyl phenyl/substituted phenylthiocarbamates^{2,3}

in 1:1 ratio in refluxing benzene, ethyl mercaptan was liberated and a colourless microcrystalline product separated out; it was crystallised from ethanol or aqueous ethanol.

(a) 1-Phenyl-3-*p*-chlorophenyl amidino carbamide: *p*-Chlorophenyl guanidine (1.7 g) and ethyl phenylthiocarbamate (1.8 g) on reaction as stated above afforded 1-phenyl-3-*p*-chlorophenylamidino carbamide (2.2 g); m.p. 189°; (Found: C, 57.1; H, 4.4; N, 19.3%; $C_{14}H_{13}N_4OCl$ requires C, 58.2; H, 4.5; N, 19.4%).

(b) 1-*p*-Chlorophenyl-3-*p*-chlorophenylamidino carbamide: *p*-Chlorophenyl guanidine (0.8 g) and ethyl *p*-chlorophenylthiocarbamate (1.0 g) on reaction as stated above afforded 1-*p*-chlorophenyl-3-*p*-chlorophenylamidino carbamide (1.3 g). It was found to sinter at 192° and melt at 339°; (Found: N, 17.0%; $C_{14}H_{12}N_4OCl_2$ requires N, 17.3%).

(c) 1-Phenyl-3-*p*-tolylamidino carbamide: *p*-Tolyl guanidine (1.0 g) and ethyl phenylthiocarbamate (0.8 g) on reaction as stated above afforded 1-phenyl-3-*p*-tolylamidino carbamide (1.3 g). It sinters at 175° and melts at 335°; (Found: C, 66.5; H, 6.0; N, 20.6%; $C_{15}H_{16}N_4O$ requires C, 67.1; H, 6.0; N, 20.8%).

(d) 1-*p*-Tolyl-3-*p*-tolylamidino carbamide: *p*-Tolyl guanidine (0.6 g) and ethyl *p*-tolylthiocarbamate (0.5 g) on reaction as above afforded 1-*p*-tolyl-3-*p*-tolylamidino carbamide (0.8 g). It was found to sinter at 215° and melt at 335° (d); (Found: C, 67.7; H, 6.5; N, 19.9%; $C_{16}H_{18}N_4O$ requires C, 68.1; H, 6.4; N, 19.9%).

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